

Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Strategy Master Plan Midterm (D4.1)

November 2023

Authors:

Regina Schwald, Dianna Bautista (ESCI)

Rosalie van Dam (WR)

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- 1 PU = Public
 PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)
 RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)
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Summary

BIOTraCes aims to concentrate on the underlying drivers of biodiversity loss by identifying the structural factors (policies, institutions, and powerful vested interests) at the root of this loss. As these factors are related to associated values and knowledge systems that support unsustainable practices and behaviours within society, the project aims to identify these aspects as well.

The project will take a collaborative approach with local initiatives to facilitate dialogue about structural factors and to bridge differing values related to biodiversity across stakeholders. This process is essential to ensure fair and legitimate outcomes for both people and nature.

The ultimate project goal is to co-produce transformative options and pathways for sustainability that are effective, equitable and just. This will result in a Theory of Transformative Change and related tools for policy making in different sectors, beyond the lifetime of the project.

The Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Strategy (DECS) Master Plan for Work package 4 (WP4) "Impact Creation" outlines a comprehensive approach to effectively communicate project findings, engage stakeholders, and ensure that the project's outcomes have a lasting impact on biodiversity-related transformative change. The plan covers a wide range of activities, from communication training and content creation to monitoring and exploitation strategies, all aimed at achieving the project's objectives and fostering positive change in society, policy, and science. The multifaceted approach will maximise the reach and influence of the project, ultimately contributing to the success and societal benefits.

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1 About BIOTraCes

BIOTraCes aims at co-producing relevant knowledge to develop approaches and strategies that contribute to transformative changes. Those are necessary to preserve and restore biodiversity in Europe. By developing a Theory of Transformative Change (ToTC), the project will enhance the understanding of the fundamental roles played by, and connections among, values, power and behaviour. Thus, it will address the underlying (indirect) drivers of biodiversity decline.

This objective will be achieved by building upon principles of pluralising, empowering, politicising and embedding (Figure 1). In addition, BIOTraCes will develop capacities for innovation and foster transformative (i.e., adaptive, plural and equitable) governance approaches to achieve just and nature-positive societies. Within the project, we will practice what we preach. We will engage with transformative initiatives in four sectors with high impact on biodiversity across Europe (Figure 1). Actions for transformation will be based on and strengthened by transdisciplinary approaches. Therefore, we devised nine case studies which represent culturally, socially, economically, politically and religiously diverse contexts and landscapes. That will also involve various marginalised perspectives, values, identities and groups. These include local and indigenous communities, women, non-white, gender+, immigrants, ethnic, economically and socially disadvantaged (age) groups. For this action, activities include forging a multilevel network of policy makers, businesses, civil-society organisations and other stakeholders, for disseminating the knowledge that we will co-produce.

The project will deliver actionable knowledge and practical tools for initiating, accelerating and upscaling just transformative changes towards nature-positive societies. In addition to this thoroughly designed project structure, we have also established an Influencer and Stakeholder Board since M11. This will further the acquired knowledge and insights in transformative biodiversity innovations, their (sectorial) surroundings, policy networks (e.g., European Commission i.r.t. Green Deal, Farm to Fork and Biodiversity Strategy) and science-policy interfaces (e.g. IPBES, IPCC).

A

B

Figure 1 BIOTraCes images A) Tree with our 4 principles; B) The four high impact sectors our research and case studies focus on

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This document is part of work package 4. WP4 focuses on the dissemination, communication and exploitation activities of the project. Its approach includes:

- Creation of a Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Strategy (DECS) (Task 4.1)
 - Elaboration of the target audiences and measure for dissemination and communication, as described in the DECS. It will be updated in M20
 - Internal communication training by ESCI to maximise the quality and effectiveness of the communication and dissemination activity among partners.
- Dissemination, engagement, clustering, and networking activities. This will be led by our partners at University of Twente (UT) (Task 4.2)
 - Publication of scientific articles, and attendance at conferences and events.
 - Dialogue with major science-policy bodies.
 - Production of policy briefs, as led by WP3
 - Final regional events in the locations of our all 9 cases.
 - A final international conference in the last three months of the project
- Communication activities including visual identity, templates, website, social media, and journalistic, audio-visual and promotional content. These actions, plus the dissemination actions will be monitored. (Task 4.3)
- Exploitation strategy as detailed and deepened in the Exploitation Roadmap and IP Management (Task 4.4)

2 Document Purpose and Scope

This Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication Strategy (DECS) plan has been developed by ESCI and the coordinators from Wageningen Environmental Research (WR) (D4.1, M12, update and final version M20). It outlines the planned actions to disseminate and exploit the project results, and the related supporting communication activities. The aim of the overarching plan is to optimise the impact of the Theory of Transformative Change and the related tools for policymaking in different sectors, beyond the lifecycle of the project.

The DECS is a living document that will evolve with the project and the generated interest of the target groups. Therefore, an update will be published in July 2024, together with the coordinators from WR. The outputs of the BIOTraCes will be consistent with the stipulations and background defined in the consortium agreement (CA) and will comply with intellectual property rights (IPR) and general data protection regulation (GDPR; EU Regulation No. 2016/679).

The purpose of the DECS is to lay out the strategies that will be used during the project. This ensures effective dissemination, exploitation and communication of the project's outputs. It maximises the impact of BIOTraCes on the various target groups. The DECS is therefore essential to increase awareness about the BIOTraCes Action Research results. To do so, four specific objectives were set (Table 1).

Table 1 The BIOTraCes Specific Objectives

Specific Objective	Description
SO1	Raise awareness and inform the various societal, policy-related, scientific and private sector target groups about the project and its results.
SO2	Engage with enabling societal actors on the project results, the proposed methods and knowledge. This will initiate innovative, biodiversity-related transformative change in society, policy and science.
SO3	Transfer detailed, targeted and co-produced knowledge. This includes information on best practices, analytical results, methodological developments as well as collaborative and action-research approaches.
SO4	Develop an exploitation plan for further research and implementation of the policy recommendations beyond the project 's lifecycle. This will ensure that BIOTraCes will have a long-lasting impact.

3 Overview

To accomplish the set goals for impact creation, dissemination and exploitation strategies are planned with a varied array of activities and different means for evaluation of the implemented actions. They are summarised in Table 2.

Table 2 Overview of the BIOTraCes Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication activities

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	Dissemination	Exploitation	Communication
Description	<p>The BIOTraCes dissemination will include selecting high-impact Open Access journals and other outlets (e.g., Open Research Europe), academic conferences, events, and workshops. The consortium will publish the results in OA journals, present the results at conferences, and make data openly available. An active dialogue and collaboration will be initiated with related EU-funded projects and initiatives on biodiversity and transformative change to share lessons learned, build capacity, avoid duplication and amplify the visibility and impact of the project. And further, (3) these actions will be monitored and evaluated through altimetric, the review of citations, and feedback forms during and after organised events.</p>	<p>The exploitation strategy will start with refining the list of Key Exploitable Results (KERs), their target groups, potential users and early adopters. Furthermore, the Intellectual Property (IP) management plan will be elaborated. These activities are the start of the development of impactful exploitation pathways to maximise impact. IP will be managed and monitored by WR. Through monitoring the policy landscape and implementing exploitation workshops, the project will refine and complete its exploitation strategy based on the project's progress.</p>	<p>The start of the communication activity will be detailing the overview of target audiences and the selection of relevant channels and key messages. ESCI has created a project website which will be the main communication platform linked to social media channels and other projects. ESCI will produce original content including journalistic articles, expert interviews, press releases, videos, infographics and social media posts. To adjust the strategy if needed to improve the effectiveness of the communication activities, ESCI will use monitoring tools to measure the actual outreach of the communication actions will be used.</p>
Actions	<p>3 joint events leading to >100 new contacts from biodiversity and transformative research and other stakeholders</p> <p>Policymakers, science-policy bodies, governments, and other BIOTraCes stakeholders: 3 policy briefs, >45 engagement activities with stakeholder groups in case locations. WP3 deliverables reaching >150 policy makers on regional, national and EU level. One final event with more than 80 stakeholders and final events in the regions with 210 participants. >1,000</p>	<p>Transfer results to major science-policy bodies.</p> <p>Definition of follow-up collaborative projects</p> <p>Upscaling inclusive strategies for transformative change</p> <p>Incorporation of project's results in education and teaching</p>	<p>Creation of visual identity</p> <p>Creation of Project website and social media channels (Milestone 2)</p> <p>Posters, roll-up, brochures</p> <p>Introduction video</p> <p>Final project video</p> <p>Nine short videos about case studies</p> <p>6+ journalistic articles</p>

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	<p>policymakers, governments, associations, and BIOTraCes partners.</p> <p>Scientific community: >600 academics, 10 peer-reviewed publications leading to >20 presentations and conference workshops.</p>		<p>5 fact sheets plus 1 page flow</p> <p>6+Quick-fire interviews</p> <p>Press releases with WR</p> <p>4 infographics</p> <p>Best Practices in Dissemination Actions (D4.4)</p> <p>Monitoring</p>
<p>Crosslinks</p>	<p>Certain actions will be backed up by communication activities. For instance, by breaking down complex scientific papers into comprehensive articles or infographics for civil society/policy makers</p>	<p>Exploitation will be supported by certain dissemination and communication actions to reach out and attract potential stakeholders. Clustering Activities will also support the exploitation, as well as the input from the Influencer and Stakeholder Board</p>	<p>Where possible communication content will be used for dissemination purposes. For instance, brochures may be handed out at conferences and infographics included in presentations.</p>

Figure 2 Overview of the BIOTraCes Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication for impact creation

4 Key Messages

Over the course of the project, messages may change or new messages may emerge. They will be thoroughly discussed within the BIOTraCes consortium and updated in M20. Currently, our tentative, relevant messages for the communication are:

1. Saving biodiversity requires significant changes in how societies and economies operate.
2. BIOTraCes will tackle the root causes of biodiversity loss by identifying the underlying drivers (including structural factors like policies, institutions, vested interests).
3. BIOTraCes will identify the structural factors and associated values and knowledge systems.
4. BIOTraCes will apply and an inclusive approach (including marginalised groups) to transform those values and knowledge systems.
5. BIOTraCes will recognise and respect diverse intersecting personalities and identities of all relevant stakeholders.
6. Through nine case studies across Europe, BIOTraCes will facilitate the dialogue about structural factors.
7. BIOTraCes will enhance the transformative potential of local innovations
8. BIOTraCes will co-produce transformative options and pathways for sustainability that are effective, equitable and just.
9. The BIOTraCes research is based on four principles: Politicising, Empowering, Pluralising, Embedding.
10. BIOTraCes will develop, implement and test a distinctive approach, the “Theory of Transformative Change” and a handbook.
11. BIOTraCes aims at creating a biodiversity movement in Europe

5 Target Groups

As a multidisciplinary project, BIOTraCes is of interest to several target groups. Our communication and dissemination actions aim to reach seven target groups. (Table 3)

Table 3 Overview of the BIOTraCes Target Groups and the associated outcomes and impacts

Target Audience	Outcome	Impact
<p>T1 Enabling players: civil society, government, education institutions, financing and business leaders</p> <p>T2 Civil society: both locally and globally: Grassroot organizations, NGOs, organisations. Including (local) transformative biodiversity initiatives</p> <p>T3 Science policy interfaces, IPBES, IPCC, CBD, IUCN</p> <p>T4 Policy networks, incl. European Commission</p> <p>T5 Scientific community</p> <p>T6 Biodiversity and Transformative research across Europe: related projects</p> <p>T7 Media, journalists</p>	<p>O1 Underpinning and embedding of knowledge on transformative change (including key elements and interdependencies SDGs) in science-policy interfaces</p> <p>O2 Increased awareness with decisive actors and enabling players about their roles in transformative change</p> <p>O3 Upscaling of processes of transformative change from case studies to other sectors, countries, networks etc.</p> <p>O4 Strengthening of thinking on transformative change in scientific community and education</p> <p>O5 Use of actionable knowledge on leverage</p> <p>O6 Access to and use of just, ethical, plural, socially inclusive strategies for propelling transformative change enabling transformative policy innovation</p> <p>O7 Access to and use of methodology on engaging and empowering a plurality of stakeholders</p> <p>O8 Improved underpinning transdisciplinary thinking and collaboration to leverage research opportunities and innovation</p>	<p>Large scale transformative change for biodiversity (including institutions, behaviours, and markets)</p> <p>A more nature positive society</p> <p>A more just society</p> <p>The recovery of biodiversity and ecosystem services</p>

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Since the start of the project in December 2022, the communication and dissemination actions have successfully reached T2 (through the activities in the 9 case studies), T5, T6 and T7. T1 and T4 respectively have also been reached, for example through the clustering activities. Efforts for all these target groups will be continued in the coming years, and in the latter half of the project focus will be more and more on SO3 and SO4 (Table 1) towards developing an exploitation plan based on the projects results.

Furthermore, we will increasingly focus on interacting and disseminating to T3 in the coming years of the project as science policy interfaces are key actors to reach the outcomes and impacts of BIOTraCes. The consortium is in good position to disseminate to science policy bodies: One of our consortium members, Esther Turnhout from the University of Twente (UT) acts as selected expert in the creation of IPBES assessments including the Land Degradation and Restoration Assessment and the Global Assessment on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services. The IPBES is an independent intergovernmental body to strengthen the science-policy interface for biodiversity and ecosystem services for the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity, long-term human well-being, and sustainable development. We aim to spread awareness about the outcomes of the project in different working groups of relevant Science Policy Bodies.

6 Dissemination Strategy

To ensure the success and visibility of BIOTraCes beyond the project range, effective dissemination and engagement are crucial. Clustering and networking activities will further spread the word on boosting biodiversity.

6.1 Dissemination Activities Overview

The BIOTraCes project will identify and quantify the most effective dissemination activities, to ensure project findings are shared as widely as possible in effective ways. Both dissemination and exploitation activities will be aligned with the needs, capacities, and networks of each consortium member. As BIOTraCes is a Research & Innovation Action (RIA), partners will dedicate efforts in publishing peer-reviewed publications in AO scientific journals and conferences that count with high an impact index. Special attention will be paid to knowledge exchange and organisation of joint dissemination activities with other projects on transformative change related to biodiversity under the destination of this call, to the European partnership on biodiversity and the Science Service and to related projects and platforms like the Biodiversity Information System for Europe (BISE), the Knowledge Centre of Biodiversity, BIODIVERSA+, Oppla, and NetworkNature. Furthermore, the consortium is specialised in engaging a plurality of different stakeholders, which will be implemented in several workshops and events in the case studies in different countries. Table 4 shows a preliminary list of dissemination activities foreseen during the project.

Table 4 Overview of the BIOTraCes Dissemination Activities

Activity	Delivery Month	Specific Objective
Scientific OA publications	M12-48	1,2, 3
<p>Key goal: Making project results and data available, share insights with academics in related fields through academic articles, books, special issues and open repositories such as GitHub and Zenodo.</p> <p>Target audience: Scientific community (researchers and students) Target journals: Nature Sustainability, Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability, Ambio, People & Nature, Society & Natural resources, Environmental Science & Policy, Land Use Policy, Environment, Development and Sustainability, Ecosystems & People, Ecology & Society, Regional Environmental Change, Ecological Economics, Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions, J. of Environmental Psychology</p>		
Presentations at conferences, workshops, and events	M10-48	1-4
<p>Key goal: Present and discuss project results. Leverage new contacts to exchange results and lay a foundation for new partnerships that will support exploitation possibilities.</p> <p>Target audience: Scientific community, policy makers, civil society, business and finance leaders</p> <p>Target events: European Ecological Economics conference, World Biodiversity Forum, European Congress of Conservation Biology, Congress of the International Society of Ethnobiology, International Conference on Environmental Psychology; Global Soil Biodiversity Conference</p>		
Collaboration and clustering with related projects and existing platforms, and engagement with SPI	M8-48	2-4
<p>Key goal: Engage in dialogue with related projects, existing platforms on biodiversity and transformative research and with science-policy interface (SPI) organisations (IPBES, IPCC, CBD, IUCN). BIOTraCes will cooperate with the EU partnership on biodiversity and Science Service (H-CL6-2021-BIODIV-01-19 H-CL6-2021-BIODIV-01-20; H-CL6-2021-BIODIV-01-10). Goals are learning and sharing knowledge, avoiding duplication of work, changing news and ideas. Joint dissemination activities will be organised, such as workshops, webinars, or outreach actions. Lead partner WR.</p> <p>Target audience: Related Horizon Europe and H2020 funded projects (HORIZON-CL6-2021-BIODIV-01-19; HORIZON-CL6-2021-BIODIV-01-20; HORIZON-CL6-2021-BIODIV-01-10), BISE, Knowledge Centre for Biodiversity, BiodivERsA, Oppla, NetworkNature</p>		

Engagement activities in the regions	M6-M48	2
<p>Key goal: Transdisciplinary analysis of transformative biodiversity initiatives and their social-ecological system, co-production of knowledge, joint testing of interventions</p> <p>Target audience: relevant stakeholders involved in the cases (e.g., transformative biodiversity innovators, civil society, policy makers, business leaders, etc.)</p>		
Engagement at EU level	M6-M48	1-4
<p>Key goal: Discuss project results and possibilities for application of transformative change thinking and strategies</p> <p>Target audience: relevant stakeholders at EU level (e.g., EU policy makers, policy makers, civil society organisations and business networks from non-participating member states)</p>		
Policy briefs	M18-M48	1,3,4
<p>Key goal: Making project results and data available in a targeted way, raise awareness about the project's results.</p> <p>Target audience: Science-policy interface organisations (IPBES, IPCC, CBD), European and national policy makers, civil society, wider stakeholder networks.</p>		
Final events in the regions (Netherlands, Portugal, Spain, Romania, Lithuania, Sweden, Hungary, Italy)	M44-48	1-4
<p>Key goal: Presenting final results and discussing their potential impact. Sparking a broader discussion about transformative change and biodiversity.</p> <p>Target audience: all stakeholders involved in the cases and invitees from their networks</p>		
Final international conference (European level)	M44-48	1-4
<p>Key goal: Presenting project's activities, final results and their impact. In-depth discussions about transformative change for addressing the biodiversity crisis.</p> <p>Target audience: All stakeholders, especially European science policy interfaces (e.g., IPBES, IPCC, CBD), EU policy makers, scientific community, educational institutions, financial and business leaders</p>		

6.2 Clustering and Networking Activities

There is growing agreement on the need for transformative change to address global challenges, such as biodiversity loss. However, there is less agreement about what transformative change entails and how it can be achieved. To address these knowledge gaps, the Horizon Europe Work Programme funded 11 Horizon Europe-funded projects with a core focus on enabling transformative change for biodiversity. The European Research Executive Agency (REA) has requested that these 'sister projects' include

collaborative activities in their workplan to better harness the synergies and common areas of work in the contexts of transformative change for biodiversity, to maximise the impact and exploitation of results of the projects and facilitate feedback to policy. Moreover, there is cooperation with other relevant EU initiatives, such as BioAgora which is setting up the Science Service for biodiversity. BIOTraCes' partners are part of other transformative change and biodiversity conservation national and international projects and networks, as for example IPBES, IPCC, Altnet, CBD. Exchange of (new) knowledge is also taking place between these initiatives. Moreover, there are the first very instructive interproject collaborations going, e.g. in a working group on values and norms.

The BIOTraCes sister projects from the European transformative change cluster are featured on the BIOTraCes website. The first collaborations have been performed by featuring our project in the newsletter of sister projects. We have been included in PLANET4B's, CLEVER and BioValue newsletters. Further collaborations have come in the form of social media activities. Our project has been featured in Transpath's social media campaign, highlighting each sister project and their objectives. In addition, there are clustering activities with our 11 sister projects as detailed in D5.8 Action Plan for Clustering Activities (WR).

6.3 Scientific Publications, Conferences and Events

Disseminating our project findings through academic and public channels is vital for reaching the scientific community and policymakers. To achieve this goal, our dissemination strategy includes:

Selecting high-impact Open Access journals and other outlets (e.g., Open Research Europe), academic conferences, events, and workshops

The consortium will publish the results in OA journals, present the results at conferences, and make data openly available. An active dialogue and collaboration will be initiated with related EU-funded projects and initiatives. Thus, our researchers will share lessons learned, build capacity and avoid duplication. In addition, this will increase the visibility and impact of the project. These actions will be monitored and evaluated through altimetric, the review of citations, and feedback forms during and after organised events.

Number of Scientific Publications

The consortium will publish a total of 15 Open Access peer-reviewed academic articles in high-impact journals across relevant scientific fields.

Conferences and Events

In addition to publications, the consortium plans to deliver 10 presentations at conferences and external events. These presentations will provide opportunities for direct engagement with experts, stakeholders, and potential collaborators. The BIOTraCes partners have been very active since the project start: University of Twente (UT) and BC3 participated and presented at the 10th IPBES plenary session. The CES took part and presented at the EMES conference. UNICT participated at the WINIR conference. The BIOTraCes head coordinator Rosalie van Dam attended the Earth System Governance conference. Zsolt Molnár from CER attended an international Herder festival and herder-scientist gathering in Hungary. Zsolt Molnár and Esther Turnhout from UT attended the UN Biodiversity COP15.

A detailed overview of conferences and events is regularly updated and filed in MS Teams site of BIOTraCes, to which partners have access.

6.4 Dialogue with Major Science-Policy Bodies

Establishing a regular and constructive dialogue with major science-policy bodies is crucial for ensuring that the project's findings inform policy decisions. To achieve this goal, we will perform the following actions:

Stakeholder Engagement

All partners will leverage their positions in bodies like IPBES, IPCC and other relevant organisations. This engagement will enable access to relevant meetings, the organisation of workshops, and hosting webinars. The goal is to facilitate direct interaction between the consortium and key decision-makers in the science-policy arena.

Policy Briefs

Translating complex research findings into accessible policy briefs is essential for bridging the gap between academia and policy-making. WP3, in collaboration with ESCI, will translate the project findings into two policy briefs. These documents will transform key insights and recommendations into concise and actionable policy guidance. In doing so, they aim to make the project results and data available in a targeted manner and discuss the potential impact of the

Final Regional Events

Organising final events in all 9 case study locations (Netherlands, Portugal, Spain, Romania, Lithuania, Sweden, Hungary, and Italy) is a critical component of stakeholder engagement and feedback gathering. The aim of these events is to present the final results of the project and the developed tools and approaches for transformative change. Round table discussions and other interactive formats will be used to gather feedback and discuss implementation opportunities.

The main target stakeholders will be the societal partners, also representing marginalised groups, as well as all other stakeholders involved in the case studies and beyond.

Final International Conference

A concluding international conference is instrumental in sharing project outcomes and engaging with a wide range of stakeholders.

The conference, to be held in the last four months of the project (M44 to M48), will target various stakeholders. This includes science-policy bodies (e.g., IPBES, IPCC), national and EU policymakers, the scientific community, universities and research centres, as well as businesses. The conference will serve as a platform to showcase the impact of the developed knowledge and methods in initiating plural, ethical, equitable, and just processes. It will present the project's activities and final results. It will also facilitate in-depth discussions on behaviour changes and actions related to biodiversity and transformative change to address the biodiversity crisis in society, policy, and the scientific community.

7 Exploitation Strategy

The aim of the work on exploitation (Task 4.4) will be to develop and deepen the initial exploitation strategies for the project's Key Exploitable Results (KERs). The exploitation strategy will towards the end of the project include a comprehensive plan for the

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coordinated exploitation of KERs and the management of intellectual property (IP) generated during the project. A detailed first version of the exploitation strategy will be described in a separate deliverable, the Exploitation Roadmap and IPR midterm (D4.6) in M20. The strategy will be updated the Exploitation Roadmap and IPR final (D4.7) due in M44.

7.1 Deepening the Exploitation Strategy

BIOTraCes exploitation is based on:

- An attractive knowledge portfolio to continue enhancing the innovations after the project end;
- A description of the steps to promote the knowledge portfolio that defines the social, policy and scientific objectives of BIOTraCes.

The portfolio of results consists of a list of KERs (Table 5)

Table 5 The BIOTraCes KERs

Preliminary Key Exploitable Results	Beneficiaries/users
Theory of Transformative Change, including values,	Science-policy bodies (IPBES, IPCC, CBD, IUCN), EU policy makers, Scientific community
Methodological toolkit for engaging and empowering a plurality of stakeholders	Science-policy bodies (IPBES, IPCC, CBD, IUCN, EU policy makers, National and regional policy makers, Civil society, Nature organisations, Cultural groups, Scientific community
Demonstration and implementation of process of transformative change in 9 EU case studies	Policy makers at the regional and national level in member states of case studies
Leverage points (opportunities for positively disrupting systems) identified	Science-policy bodies (IPBES, IPCC, CBD, IUCN, EU policy makers, National and regional policy makers, Civil society, Scientific community
Just, ethical, plural, socially inclusive strategies for propelling transformative change	Science-policy interface bodies (IPBES, IPCC, CBD, IUCN, EU policy makers, National and regional policy makers, Civil society, Scientific community
Key elements of transformative change for biodiversity, developed via EU-interproject collaboration	Science-policy interface bodies (IPBES, IPCC, CBD, IUCN)
Knowledge on biodiversity interdependencies in SDGs	EU policy makers, Scientific community

Transdisciplinary learning community	Scientific community and education institutes
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The exploitation roadmap include individual and joint efforts and related organisation of such collaborative efforts (partnership policy and governance). It will describe the consortiums plans to do further research, promote results, and influence policy after the project ends, among other things. The following steps will be taken to come to a final exploitation plan:

Analysis of Opportunities:

The task will involve a thorough analysis of opportunities for exploitation in science, policy, and society. This analysis will identify gaps in existing practices and propose areas where the project's findings can be leveraged to drive transformative change.

Planning of the next steps:

Partners will collaborate to plan the next steps for fully exploiting project results. This includes formulating proposals for continued work, establishing governance structures to facilitate joint exploitation, and creating a roadmap for ongoing partnership activities.

Organisational Structure:

Partners will define the organisational structure for joint exploitation efforts, specifying roles, responsibilities, and decision-making processes.

Promotion Activities:

Strategies for promoting the exploitation of results will be outlined in line with the communication and dissemination strategy, including engagement with stakeholders, and outreach efforts that are specifically targeted to support exploitation of the BIOTraCes results.

7.2 Intellectual Property (IP) Management

Main type of IP generated in BIOTraCes are methodologies, know-how and tools. Each Horizon-funded research project such as BIOTraCes is obligated to examine the possibility of protecting its results and must adequately protect them – for an appropriate period and with appropriate territorial coverage.

The task will address the protection and responsible management of project-related IP. The IP Helpdesk of the EC defines five pillars of knowledge (IP) management in Horizon projects: 1) IP used in the project (background access and usage rights); 2) IP generated by the project (result/foreground ownership); 3) IP assessment (market opportunities, possible protection strategies); 4) IP protection (e.g. copyrights); 5) IP dissemination and exploitation (in research, education, commercial, policy). All 5 will be taken into account in the IP management process and development of an IP protection strategy.

Risk Assessment:

Potential risks in the exploitation of project-related IP will be identified and assessed. This includes understanding the impact of these risks and anticipating corrective actions to mitigate them. As part of the assessment, a proposition of optimal IPR protection options, in line with obtained results will be developed.

8 Communication Strategy

To create a unique BIOTraCes identity and boost the visibility during the lifecycle of the project and beyond, ESCI has been and will create a wide range of communication activities. The main aim of the communication activities will be to raise awareness, inform and increase visibility of the BIOTraCes project and its solutions to relevant stakeholders and the public at large. This will be done through creating compelling and meaningful content that will convey accessible messages about the project's activities, its results, implications and benefits. Social media channels (e.g. X/Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube) and the BIOTraCes website are used for wide communication, and more specialised channels (e.g. special interest magazines) to reach out to specialists audiences (e.g. civil society, policy makers, NGOs), as well as the local media (e.g. local newspapers, radio and TV) to reach out to society at large.

8.1 Branding

BIOTraCes has been "branded" with a unique visual identity. A strong, attractive and consistent visual identity facilitates communication, dissemination and exploitation activities. In this way, it assures a design that is easily identified. Stakeholders will quickly attribute content to the project which can foster engagement and dialogue. The branding includes the project logo, a colour code and fonts. These elements have been used when creating project material.

Tagline

A tagline was created for BIOTraCes: "Connecting for Biodiversity". This reflects two main aspects of the project: society and nature – united for boosting biodiversity. The tagline gives an idea and as such will help to attract attention from relevant stakeholders.

Logo

A simple and modern logo was developed (Figure 3). Its elements, including the feet and the leaves, reflect the two main aspects of BIOTraCes: Society and biodiversity. All versions exist with and without the tagline. The logo must not be altered or adapted and care must be taken to not distort the dimensions. The logo is available in multiple versions including a white or transparent background or with a green background.

Colour Code

A set of primary colours was chosen to be primarily used for project content. These are complemented with a set of secondary colours. The green tones, reflect the biodiversity and nature. These colours can be used to convey information at different levels of importance based on the effect of the colours (Figure 3).

Figure 3 A) The BIOTraCes logo in white; B) The BIOTraCes logo in green; C) The BIOTraCes colour code

Fonts and Variation of English

The main font of the project is Verdana. For purposes of consistency and according to EU- requirements. it is recommended to adhere to British English spelling conventions where possible.

Funding Acknowledgement

Communication and dissemination content must display the EU Horizon emblem and the following text as per Grant Agreement:

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European

Commission. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

8.2 Templates

Different templates – such as this deliverable template, a report template, a Powerpoint template, and a Meeting Minutes template - were created following the visual identity of BIOTraCes for consistency and easy recognition by stakeholders. The template available in the BIOTraCes Teams-Folder. They can be used for communication, dissemination and exploitation activities as necessary (Figure 4).

Figure 4 The BIOTraCes templates: A) The powerpoint; B) The simple word document; C) The meeting minutes; D) The deliverable template

8.3 Communication Channels

8.3.1 Online Presence

Website

Since February 2023 (M3), the BIOTraCes website is online. It serves as a "digital anchor" for the content of BIOTraCes. The website's purpose is to fulfil goals of the DECS and to serve as a point of information for all relevant stakeholders. It explains the BIOTraCes concept and features our nine case studies across Europe. The website is regularly updated with news about the project. We are currently creating a new section where we will feature the societal partners of our case studies. In addition, two new sections will be created under the "Results": public deliverables and scientific publications. Communication material such as articles, graphics, or videos have been and will be uploaded to the page. dissemination and exploitation content such info about workshops are placed on the website, too. Where appropriate, material such as certain

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public deliverables or graphics will be provided for download. The website is also supported by social media activities which link back to the page. This helps attract visitors and increase awareness about the project. (Figure 5) Through our website and social media activities, we aim for over 500 followers, 12,000 web visits / year, 35.000 impressions in total on social media accounts and webpage. These activities fulfil specific objectives 1-4 of this DECS. (See Section 2. Document Purpose and Scope).

Social Media

Social media is a good tool to get in contact with all relevant stakeholders and stay connected with them on a regular basis. Different social media platforms are used to spread information to relevant stakeholders and engage with them. This has already built a community of interested stakeholders and early adopters of BIOTraCes. Furthermore, it fosters interests and trust. All channels have the same account name: BIOTraCes. This allows interested stakeholders to easily find the project on different platforms. Regular posts along with dedicated social media campaigns (such as the current "Faces" campaign) will build a community of relevant stakeholders. The project website contains plugins to all social media channels, helping to attract followers. All the consortium partners are also encouraged to invite stakeholders to follow the BIOTraCes accounts, to share posts among their community and to actively post themselves about the project and their involvement (Figure 5).

LinkedIn

LinkedIn is the top online platform for professionals with more than 830 million members worldwide. It is used to search jobs, connect to professionals, strengthen professional relationships and learn relevant career skills. It has also been a strong platform for Horizon-funded projects. The LinkedIn BIOTraCes channel (Figure 5) is active since the project's start in December 2022 (M1). Since then, it has successfully created a dedicated and active community of scientists, societal partner and NGOs. To attract our target groups to the LinkedIn and Twitter account, news about the project is shared regularly. Further, the account will be used to promote dissemination and exploitation activities. For instance, by sharing conferences, insights from our research team (such as the PhD defence of project member Audra Balundé or the Faces-campaign).

X (formerly Twitter)

X (formely Twitter) is an online news and social networking site with over 368 million monthly active users worldwide. Similar to LinkedIn, X's membership has a high share of highly educated persons. The X account @Biotraces_EU (Figure 5) is active since the project's start (M1) and will be used to attract scientists, grassroot organisations, our societal partners, science-policy interfaces and journalists to the project. Due to the new X/policies, the BIOTraCes consortium was discussing a potential switch from X to Facebook. A final decision will be made at the beginning of 2024.

Instagram and Facebook

Instagram is a photo and video sharing platform with over 2 billion active users worldwide. The Instagram account @biotraces (Figure 5) is live since the BIOTraCes project start on December 1, 2022 (M1). The content is tailored to the target audiences to ensure that it is comprehensive for non-experts.

As previously mentioned, a decision about a potential Facebook page will be made in the beginning of 2024.

A

B

C

D

Figure 5 The BIOTraCes online platforms: A) The project webpage; B) The LinkedIn account; C) The Twitter account; D) The Instagram account

YouTube

The video sharing website YouTube has more than 2 billion viewers worldwide. The platform will be used to publish and promote video content about the project. Videos will be published by ESCI to make use of ESCI's followers. This ensures a greater reach as compared to starting from scratch with a new YouTube channel. The ESCI YouTube channel performs very successfully: It has 1150 subscribers and an array of 122 videos. So far, ESCI has published the introductory video for BIOTraCes on July 18, 2023. The film has reached 684 views which is a very good number for such a specialised project.

Zenodo

A Zenodo community (Figure 6) for BIOTraCes was made in October 2023 (M10) by our partners at Mykolas Romeris University (MRU). Zenodo is an open access repository where users can upload scientific papers and other data relevant to the project. Individual partners will select a data steward who is responsible for the upload of material.

Figure 6 The BIOTraCes Zenodo account

8.3.2 Promotional Content

Creating promotional materials is essential for increasing the visibility and outreach of the project. For this purpose, our communication strategy includes the production of visual and audio-visuals content. The audio-visual content, in particular, is a powerful medium to convey the project messages. These activities fulfil specific objectives 1-4 of this DECS. (See Section 2. Document Purpose and Scope).

Visuals: Infographics

Four infographics will be developed to display complex project findings and insights into visually appealing and easy-to-understand formats. These infographics will be shared across the BIOTraCes communication channels to engage a wider audience. If need be, they can also be used as posters in conferences and seminars. ESCI created the first infographic based on the already existing designs in M9. It provides an overview of the nine case studies, the “core” of the BIOTraCes action research (Figure 7).

Visuals: Factsheets

ESCI will provide concise summaries of key project aspects, such as case studies, methodologies, and results. These factsheets will serve as quick reference materials for stakeholders seeking essential project information. They can also be distributed in conferences and at events. The first fact sheet is currently being designed and revised by ESCI. The proposed content is about the key principles of BIOTraCes. As a new and special feature, there is a QR code that allows info on where and when it was activated. The first fact sheet is currently being designed and revised by ESCI.

Visuals: Flyer/Poster

Flyers and posters are a great tool to further promote the project goals and results. They can be used online for social media or printed for seminars and conferences. Prior to the project start, WR has created this flyer as a comprehensive overview of the BIOTraCes project goals and principles (Figure 7).

B

Figure 7 A) The BIOTraCes infographic B) The BIOTraCes flyer

Audio-Visuals: Introductory video

ESCI produced an introductory video that explains the project's objectives. The video serves as an engaging and accessible entry point for stakeholders, including biodiversity innovators, universities, policy makers, and science-policy bodies. The background story features the WR case study, the planned building of an eco-community in Wageningen. The film was aired on 5 July, 2023 (M8) on the BIOTraCes social media channels, the website and the ESCI YouTube channel. It reached 675 views – which is, compared to related projects, an excellent number. The film performed exceedingly well on LinkedIn where it reached 1.352 impressions.

Audio Visuals: Short case study videos

Every consortium partner produced a video of their case studies. These 9 videos showcased the unique challenges and solutions implemented in each case study, making the project's work more relatable and understandable to a broader audience. The videos were produced prior to the in-person meeting in M4 and published consecutively on social media between May-August 2023.

Audio Visuals: Final project video

A final video will be created to summarise the project's results in an impactful way. It will include testimonials from stakeholders, highlighting transformative biodiversity innovations (D4.5). This video will target biodiversity innovators, universities, policy makers, and science-policy bodies.

Audio Visuals: Page flow

A page-flow was designed to visually depict the project's processes and impact pathways. This visual aid will help stakeholders grasp the project's complexity and potential for transformative change. It is also a very intuitive, easy to handle tool which combines text and video in slides. The page flow was published in M10 and will be updated according to the project's development and research results.

Supporting Promotional Materials

Additional materials, including posters, roll-up banners, brochures, and a project flyer, will be developed to further strengthen the project's visibility and outreach. So far, the draft version of the roll-up and fact sheet has been created as well as the first infographic. WR has already designed a flyer prior to the official project start (Figure 7). These materials will be strategically distributed at events, conferences, and other relevant venues.

8.3.3 Journalistic Content

Creating engaging and informative journalistic content is essential for capturing the attention of stakeholders and the wider public. Thus, ESCI has and will produce high-quality journalistic content including journalistic articles, interviews and press releases. Through these actions we aim for 30.000 downloads, views, reads and impressions on different channels (online, print). These activities fulfil specific objectives 1-4 of this DECS. (See Section 2. Document Purpose and Scope).

Press Releases

Press releases will be written and published to announce important milestones of the project. An initial press release was published in M1 to announce the launch of the project.

Journalistic Articles

Six professionally produced journalistic articles will be crafted to communicate project findings and insights in an accessible and engaging manner. These articles will target relevant online platforms. So far, ESCI has already published three articles (Table 6). Additionally, the project was featured as part of an Earth.Org article about agriculture.

Quick-Fire Interviews

In addition to the articles, ESCI will conduct six quick-fire interviews with experts from our consortium in transformative change and biodiversity. These interviews (Table 6) will offer concise and insightful perspectives on project-related topics and will be published across various media channels, including partner websites, newsletters, and relevant magazines. So far, ESCI has released one quick-fire interview in written form with Dr. Zsolt Molnar, a consortium member from Ökológiai Kutatóközpont, the Hungarian Centre for Ecological Research (CER). In addition, ESCI has conducted another quick-fire interview with the BIOTraCes head coordinator Rosalie von Dam. It was published as "coffee-talk" in M11 and highlights her approach to BIOTraCes.

Table 6 The BIOTraCes articles and interviews

Overview Articles and Interviews			
Article or Interview	Title	Publication Date	Publication Location
Article	May I introduce myself? I am Balint's hat!	June 27, 2023	The BIOTraCes website
Article	The hidden knowledge that could help us manage the biodiversity crisis	July 5, 2023	Inside Ecology
Interview	Tapping traditional herder's wisdom to nurture biodiversity	August 5, 2023	University World News
Article	Europe's Agricultural Future May Lie in Both Innovative and Ancient Farming Practices	September 5, 2023	Earth.Org
Article	5 years of Fridays for Future: Researchers say climate strikes bring slow but sure change	September 15, 2023	Euronews.green
Interview	Coffee-Talk with Rosalie von Dam "Practice what you preach"	November 13, 2023	The BIOTraCes website

8.4 Internal Communication

Communication inside the consortium is facilitated by the coordinator. Planned general meetings, when not in person, are organised via Teams (Microsoft). WP and other necessary meetings are regularly taking place to keep the information flow within the consortium. The documents/recordings of the minutes are shared in Teams. This activity fulfils specific objectives 1 of this DECS. (See Section 2. Document Purpose and Scope).

8.5 Communication Training

Helping the consortium partners to efficiently interact with journalists and media (press inquiries for interviews, press releases) increases the awareness about BIOTraCes among relevant stakeholders. Thus, ESCI held a communication training about journalistic basics at the first live consortium meeting at WR in M4. This activity fulfils Milestone 3 (Annex B) as described in the Grant Agreement.

8.6 Best Practices of Communication and Dissemination Actions

The results of the communication and dissemination actions will be published in a report in July 2026 (M44). This report (D4.4) will highlight and describe the best communication and dissemination strategies. The reports will serve as inspiration for communication and dissemination actions to other European projects.

8.7 Approval Requirements

According to the GA annex 5 page 10/11, all partners are required to give at least 15 days advance notice to the other beneficiaries (unless agreed otherwise), together with sufficient information on the results they plan to disseminate. Online presence, promotional and journalistic content such as social media posts, brochures, graphics and articles require a different approval procedure than scientific articles. No approval is needed for social media posts created by the partners. The coordinator will be asked to approve promotional content. This will ensure the accuracy of the material and that confidentiality is not breached. If the content is based on specific expertise from another partner, approval will be asked from them. Press releases from partners will be under their responsibility. It is recommended to inform the communication manager about it, so the press release can be promoted through the social media channels of the project. For journalistic content, only the organisations or persons mentioned in the publication will be approached to fact-check and approve the content.

9 Summary of Key Performance Indicators

Several key performance indicators were identified for specific communication and dissemination actions. They are summarised below:

- 15 peer-reviewed scientific publications, reaching 400 scientists and researchers presentations at events, reaching 600 scientists
- 2 joint events (workshops/webinars), 2 workshops with SPI organisations / policy >100 new contacts from biodiversity and transformative research and other stakeholders
- 6 journalistic articles, 6 expert interviews, and press releases resulting in 30.000 downloads, views, reads and impressions on different channels (online, print)
- Original content published on social media, resulting in >500 followers and 12,000 web visits / year, 35.000 impressions in total on social media accounts and webpage
- 5+ workshops per case study at local and if relevant at national level (>45 workshops in total)
- 1 gender & intersectionality workshop
- 2 policy briefs >45 engagement activities with stakeholder groups in case locations. WP3 deliverables reaching >150 policy makers on regional, national and EU level
- 80+ stakeholders at international conference – One final event with more than 80 stakeholders and final events in various regions >1,000 policymakers, governments, associations, and BIOTraCes partners
- 35.000 impressions (views on screen) on the website/social media >600 academics, 10 peer-reviewed publications leading to >20 presentations and conference workshops

10 Monitoring

To ensure that communication efforts are effective and adaptable, ESCI has established robust monitoring mechanisms.

Website Analytics

A GDPR-compliant version of Google Analytics called “Matomo” was implemented to track website performance. This provides detailed insights into website traffic, user behaviour, and engagement levels.

Social Media Monitoring

The BIOTraCes social media channels X/Twitter and LinkedIn, are being monitored with the Falcon/brandwatch tool. This tracks engagement metrics, such as likes, shares, comments, and follower growth. The data is used to assess the impact of social media campaigns and tailor content accordingly.

Event Surveys

Satisfaction surveys will be conducted at events, including conferences and regional gatherings. These surveys will collect feedback from participants, helping to evaluate the effectiveness of event communication and identify areas for improvement.

Reporting and Analysis

Data collected through monitoring mechanisms will be analysed regularly to evaluate the impact of communication and dissemination actions. Insights gained will be used to optimise ongoing activities, ensuring that the project reaches its target audiences effectively. They will also feed into the Deliverable D4.4 Best Practices of Communication and Dissemination Actions in July 2026 (M44). Detailed monitoring data can be found on the ESCI database and BIOTraCes Teams.

11 Expected Impact

The planned dissemination, exploitation and communication actions will help to reach the BIOTraCes impacts (Table 7).

Table 7 Overview of the project’s expected impacts

Impact	Who/What will benefit
<p>I1. Large scale transformative change for biodiversity:</p> <p>Transformative changes are gaining momentum across sectors, groups, landscapes and member states, in a fair,</p>	<p>See I2. below</p>

<p>inclusive and pluralised way, leading to I2 and I3 and ultimately to I4.</p>	
<p>I2. More nature-positive society:</p> <p>Biodiversity-positive values, behaviours, lifestyles and policies are wide-spread within Europe and beyond. A wide range of high-impact sectors and their markets are transformed and have become more resilient. Markets and patterns of production and consumption are re-embedded in social and ecological norms. Nature-based solutions are standard practice and benefits society by creating economic opportunities and multiple public health and wellbeing benefits as well as bringing people closer to nature.</p>	<p>Corporations which have integrated biodiversity (sensu nature-positive) into their business strategies</p> <p>Civil society organisations striving for sustainability and environmental justice.</p>
<p>I3 A more just society:</p> <p>Marginalised groups have been empowered to raise their voice, and the plurality of people and values is accepted. Development of policies and value chains is inclusive and human rights are respected. Power, employment, benefits and access to ecosystem services and nature-based solutions are fairly distributed across social groups and regions and within value chains. Social and environmental justice are prioritised over continued growth in demand for natural resources and energy.</p>	<p>Local and indigenous communities, women, non-white, gender+, immigrants, ethnic, economically and socially disadvantaged (age) groups</p> <p>Society at large will benefit from socially and environmentally just transformative innovations.</p>
<p>I4 Recovery of biodiversity and ecosystem services:</p> <p>As a result of changed land use (rewilding, biodiversity-friendly agriculture, intensification of landscape features, greening cities etc.), sustainable harvesting, less pollution etc.</p>	<p>Biodiversity in natural areas and in man-made landscapes including agricultural areas and cities, within EU and in countries where imported products are produced.</p> <p>All will benefit from a higher level of delivery of a broader range of ecosystem services.</p>

Annex

a) Overview of WP4 Deliverables

Table 8 Overview of WP4 deliverables

Del. No.	Deliverable name	WP No.	Lead beneficiary	Nature	Dissemination level	Delivery date from Annex I (project month)	Delivered Yes/No	Actual / Forecast delivery date
D4.1	Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication Strategy (DECS) masterplan midterm	WP4	ESCI	R — Document, report	PU-Public	M12	Yes	M12
D4.2	Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication Strategy (DECS) masterplan final	WP4	ESCI	R — Document, report	PU-Public	M20	No	M20
D4.3	Workshop reports	WP4	UT	Other	PU-Public	M44	No	M44
D4.4	Best practices of Communication and Dissemination Actions (numbers of downloads, involvement, etc.)	WP4	ESCI	DEC — Websites, patent filings, videos, etc	PU-Public	M44	No	M44
D4.5	Video with testimonies of transformative biodiversity innovations	WP4	ESCI	DEC — Websites, patent filings, videos, etc	PU-Public	M44	No	M44

D4.1 DECS Master Plan (Midterm)

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D4.6	Exploitation Roadmap and IPR midterm	WP4	WR	R — Document, report	PU-Public	M20	No	M20
D4.7	Exploitation Roadmap and IPR final	WP4	WR	R — Document, report	PU-Public	M44	No	M44

b) Overview of WP4 Milestones

Table 9 Overview of WP4 milestones

MilestoneNo.	Milestone name	Work package No.	Lead beneficiary	Delivery date from Annex I	Achieved Yes/No	Actual / Forecast achievement date	Comments
2	Launch of our website	WP4	ESCI	M4	Yes	M3	The associated social media channels launched in M1. The website was made live in M3.
3	Communication training	WP4	ESCI	M6	Yes	M4	The communication training was performed during the live meeting in M4